

COMMUNICATIVE METHOD – A NEW APPROACH IN THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The article discusses the advantages and disadvantages of different methods of teaching foreign languages. Language teaching has been around for many centuries, and over the centuries it has changed. About 500 years ago, Latin was the world's most widely studied foreign language. It was the dominant language of education, commerce, religion, and government in the Western world. Then French, Italian, and English replaced Latin due to political changes. [1] England in the 1500-1700 children went to "grammar schools" where they studied foreign language through memorization. This meant there was lots of grammar, memorization and translation and no real communication. This Article considers an overview of the development in Foreign Language Teaching for real communication rather than learning systems of grammar and vocabulary. Recently, most of teaching instructors are focuses more on the process of teaching, and understanding how to create lessons drawing on whatever you have been taught, whatever teaching context is and ever whatever you have come up with on your own as a basis for teaching practice. Consequently, now English is considered a global language and is taught as a main foreign language in different parts of the world.*

Keywords: *communicative competence, text-based teaching, linguistic competence, cultural background, inductive method, deductive principles.*

КОММУНИКАТИВНЫЙ МЕТОД – НОВЫЙ ПОДХОД В ПРАКТИКЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются преимущества и недостатки различных методов обучения иностранным языкам. Преподавание языка существует уже много веков, и на протяжении столетий оно менялось. Около 500 лет назад латынь была самым широко изучаемым иностранным языком в мире. Это был доминирующий язык образования, торговли, религии и правительства в западном мире. Затем французский, итальянский и английский заменили латынь из-за политических изменений. [1] Англия в 1500-1700 годах дети ходили в «гимназии», где изучали иностранный язык путем запоминания. Это означало, что было много грамматики, запоминания и перевода и никакого реального общения. В этой статье рассматривается обзор развития преподавания иностранных языков для реального общения, а не для изучения систем грамматики и лексики. В последнее время большинство инструкторов по обучению больше сосредотачиваются на процессе обучения и понимании того, как создавать уроки, опираясь на то, чему вас учили, какой бы ни был учебный контекст и что бы вы ни придумали самостоятельно в качестве основы для педагогической практики. Следовательно, сейчас английский язык считается глобальным языком и преподается как основной иностранный язык в разных уголках мира.*

Ключевые слова: *коммуникативная компетенция, текстовое обучение, языковая компетенция, культурный фон, индуктивный метод, дедуктивные принципы.*

INTRODUCTION

The article discusses different methods and describes effective principles of “Communicative Language Teaching”. What is Communicative Language Teaching and how we can use this method of speaking? This approach aims to make communicative competence the goal of language teaching and to develop procedures for teaching the four language skills, includes listening, reading, writing and speaking. Furthermore, we developed communicative competence through making communication and this focus of the classroom activities, which is the peer work, group work with students by product of using language to communicate. In order to do this activities have to be developed that enable students to practice communicating in a different ways according to the language proficiency level through tasks, through focusing on role plays, through information sharing activities. Activities of that kind which require students to draw on their communicative resources and try to make communication possible in the classroom.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

CLT is essentially a set of general principles that refers to how communication can be the focus of teaching and learning and which attributes the acquisition of communicative competence to providing opportunities for students to practice communicating through their classroom materials . CLT is alive and well today, it is taken different forms in recent years and some context it is led to what we call task based teaching in others. In addition, this approach is believed of text-based teaching or and others led to content based teaching which is depends on other podcasts. Most of the instructors believed this method and it important for us to consider today. The following questions are also aimed to be answered in the paragraphs below:

- 1 What methodology often use of Communicative Approach?
- 2 What are the differences between the previous and current methods of communication?
- 3 Why should a teachers or learners understand and learn Communicative Method?

“Communicative Language Teaching”

Communicative Language Teaching is one of the top influenced approaches to language teaching today. Many language teachers when you ask them to identify what methodology they use they often mention communicative as the methodology of choice however when pressed to give a more detailed account of what they mean by communicative their explanations tend to vary does this mean teaching conversation, does it mean an absence of grammar in a course or perhaps an emphasis on open – ended discussion activities as the main features of a course”.

Communicative language teaching can be understood as a set of principles, and the set of principles forms a particular method. It is true that though CLT is the well-researched, and instructors globally practiced method in English language teaching today. Most teachers would like to examine each of these issues , perhaps in a little more detail communicative language teaching set as it is goal the teaching of what is called communicative competence .

Communicative competence can be contrasted with linguistic or grammatical competence, which really focuses on sentence formation and the ability to produce grammatically correct sentences. Linguistic competence does not really describe how we use language as a basis for communication this is the focus of communicative competence. And communicative competence includes a number of different dimensions of language knowledge in use for example, knowing how to use a language for a range of different purposes and functions knowing how to vary our use of language according to the setting who we are talking

to and informal or formal speech style is appropriate. It also refers to how we can use language as a medium for cross – cultural communication interacting with people from different cultural backgrounds. In other cases, knowing how to produce different types of texts such as narratives reports, interviews or conversations. It shows that how we can maintain communication despite having limitations in one’s language proficiency through perhaps using different kinds of communication strategies. Communicative language teaching also reflects an understanding of what processes of second language learning consist of, and these processes include things such as the following interaction between the learner and the users of the language collaborative creation of meaningful and purposeful interaction through language. It means that learning through negotiation of meaning as the learner and the arrived at understanding. Learning are paying attention to the feedback and learners get when they use the languages . In some cases, noticing paying attention to the language one hers and trying to incorporate new forms into ones developing communicative competence.

RESULTS

Communicative method refers to the ability to try out and experiment with different ways of explaining the same topic.

“In 1966, the linguist and anthropologist Dell Hymes developed the concept of communicative competence, which redefined what it meant to “know” a language”[2]

At present time when CLT began there was a movement away from traditional lesson formats where the focus was on mastery of different items of grammar and practice through controls activities such as , memorization of dialogues drills. The use of it in CLT this moved towards the use of peer work activities in project work , so a movement away from accuracy based activities if you like towards more influence communicative based activities the type of classroom activities proposed, then also implied new roles in the classroom for teachers and learners . Learners now had to participate in classroom activities they were based on cooperative rather than an individualistic approach to learning. They had to become comfortable with listening to their peers in group of work or pair work tasks rather than relying solely on the teacher for a model they were expected to take on a greater degree of responsibility for their own learning.

“The time has come establish a new system for teaching foreign languages in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive country, from now on school, lyceum, college and university graduates must know at least 2 foreign languages perfectly. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of every educational institution,” said Shavkat Mirziyoyev President of Uzbekistan [3]

“To promote English language instruction in our country, CLT was introduced at the national level in the early 2000s. To date, a select number of studies have discussed the outcomes of these pedagogical reforms. It has shown that CLT is not fully implemented in language classrooms, especially in rural towns. Furthermore, the attention paid to the issue of language in our country, in particular, the efforts to preserve our mother tongue, are in essence aimed at realizing the unfulfilled dreams of our enlightened scientists. It is incomparable in terms of practical actions. It is known to everyone that in the process of integration into the world community, at the time of bold and active entry into the world, the need for knowledge of foreign languages naturally increases. Therefore, today the criteria of all round maturity of a

specialist in the field require that it should know several foreign languages in addition to his native language. It is shown that teachers may face a number of problems and obstacles teaching communicative method in foreign languages. The problems of teaching foreign languages are inextricably linked with the issues that need to be solved regarding the education of the mother tongue. It is no secret that the oral and written literacy of graduates of general secondary schools has decreased. It is difficult to ask a student who has not mastered the rules and regulations of their native language to master a foreign language at a high level. Therefore, improving the quality and efficiency of teaching the mother tongue in high school not only serves as a basis for students to acquire a foreign language at the required level. For this, the need to develop the technique of fluent communication in foreign languages and use the CLT method was considered as a solution". [4]

Teachers now had to assume the role of facilitator and monitor rather than being a model for correct speech and writing and one of the primary responsibilities of making students avoid errors the teacher had to develop a different view of learners errors and of his or her own role in facilitating of language learning . In the other ways, influence of CLT theory grammar based methodologies such as audio lingual gave way to more functional and skill based teaching and at the same time accuracy activities, such as drilling were replaced by activities based on interactive small group work. As you can imagine communicative language teaching created a great deal of excitement when it first appeared as a new approach to language teaching in the 1990 and 1992 language teachers and teaching institutions in UZBEKISTAN . In 2015 began to rethink they are teaching their syllabuses their classroom and materials.

In planning language courses within a communicative approach grammar was no longer the starting point new approaches to language teaching and language course development were needed. It was argued that learners learn a language through the process of communication in it and that communication that meaningful to the learner provides a better opportunity for learning, then through a grammar based approach new techniques were needed. As I mentioned new roles for teachers, new roles to the learner so instead of focusing on accurate repetition and memorization of sentences and grammatical practice. At present activities that required learners to negotiate meaning and to interact meaningfully were required since the 1990 the communicative approach has been widely implemented. But because it describes a set of very general principle grounded in the notion of communicative competence is the goal of second and foreign language teaching and learning and as well as the use of a communicative syllabus and methodology , because of these general goals . It is continued to evolve as our understanding of the process of second language learning has developed current communicative language teaching theory and practice thus draws on a number of different educational paradigms (The Paradigm of Education) and traditions.

Educational paradigm is understood as framework of key provisions and the ideas which are acknowledged by the pedagogical public during the concrete time period and are the cornerstone of scientific research. This paradigm focuses on developing the whole child, not just developing them in academics. This includes, developing them socially and emotionally so that they learn to develop the soft skills needed for success in the future [5].

DISCUSSION

Communicative approach draws on a number of diverse sources there is no single or agreed upon set of practices that characterize current communicative approaches. CLT today

refers to a set of generally agreed upon principles that can be applied in different ways depending on the teaching context the age of learners their level, their learning goals and so on. So current approaches methodology draw on earlier traditions in CLT and continue to make reference to some extent to traditional approaches as well .

Professor (Jack C. Richards) said : “For those language teachers who pride themselves on forming deep bonds with their students , the CLT method can be a powerful way to engage and support learners. Everyone in the classroom can practice forming questions by finding out information from their peers, and perhaps the combined wisdom of the classroom could help resolve some of the challenges international students might be facing”. [6]

CLT lessons priorities the use of teaching techniques that require learners to respond to real world environments and situations. Group and pair work are therefore particularly relevant and widely used activities to bring language learning to life.

Classroom activities typically have some of these characteristics they seek to develop student’s communicative competence through linking grammatical development to the ability to communicate [7]. So grammar is not taught in isolation but often arises out of a communicative task thus creating a need for specific items of grammar students might carry out a task and then reflect on some of the linguistic characteristics of their performance. In the classroom activities for the requiring the communication , interaction and negotiation of meaning are made use of these include problem – solving activities, information sharing role-play and task based activities and these provide opportunities for both inductive as well as a deductive learning of grammar. Inductive method including inquiry learning, problem based learning, discovery learning that focuses on the student. For example, Instructor might use or show a few examples of a grammar point in English and then ask students what they notice. Deductive principles of this approach are generally used in the classes where the main target is to teach grammar structures. For instance, Teacher writes simple sentences to explain the rules of the past and present tenses. After this they hand out worksheets where in students are asked to convert past tense to present tense and vice versa. It is a teacher-centered approach to presenting new content. Activities also seek to employ content that connects to students lives and interests they also allow students to personalize learning by applying what they have learned to their own lives and classroom materials typically most use of make use of authentic texts , authentic sources. The internet is for fighting a great deal of source for language teaching materials different syllabus types within the communicative orientation to language teaching employ different routes to developing communicative competence . As I said earlier this led to proposals for the organization of syllabuses in terms of functions and notions rather than simply in terms of grammatical structures. Later the focus shifted to procedures for identifying learners communicative needs and this resulted in proposals to make needs analysis an essential communicative an essential component of communicative methodology. As I mentioned methodologist focused on the kinds of classroom activities that could be used to implement a communicative approach such as group of work , task work and information gap activities .

CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, Communicative language teaching an approach which developed as a reaction away from grammar focused approaches to teaching really gave priority to accuracy and to the sentence as the unit of presentation and practice in the classroom. CLT argues of course that goal of language learning is communicative competence and that we develop

communicative competence through communication focus of the classroom. In order to do this activates have to be developed that enable students to practice communicative in a different ways according to the proficiency level through tasks, focusing on role plays, through information sharing activates. Activities of that which kind require students to draw on their communicative resources and try to make communication possible in the classroom. At present in Uzbekistan CLT is developing a set of general principles refers to how need to learn foreign language and need to focus of teaching, learning. As I mentioned that It rules to providing opportunities for students to practice second language through their classroom materials. It is taken different forms in recent years in some context led to what we call task based teaching. I think CLT still important for us to develop our speech in foreign language.

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